

MANAGEMENT PERSPECTIVES OF INNOVATIONS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION IN NIGERIAN EDUCATION THE WAY FORWARD

Veronica Egonekwu Mogboh, Ph.D, Eneh Nnamdi Sunday Ph.D.

Department of Educational Foundations, Godfrey Okoye University, Enugu

E-mail: nekwuvero@yahoo.ca

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15706298>

ABSTRACT: This chapter examines management perspectives of innovations and entrepreneurship education in Nigerian education: The way forward. It discusses the importance of innovation in education management and reveals entrepreneurship education as a potential strategy to battle unemployment, retrenchment. It serves as a tool for social, economic and societal, even global development. More so, the prevalent health and social circumstance of COVID-19 Pandemic has generated obvious changes in the world in all spheres of life. The natural focus on education is not misplaced if it can successfully navigate the survival of people and bring about some order in society on equitable parallel with galloping technological development. This chapter draws attention to the need in the management and implementation of entrepreneurship education in Nigerian education and the challenges facing it. It concludes with the ways of implementing sustaining and promoting innovation and entrepreneurship education by suggesting various options including that Nigerian government should emulate Western countries like Israel, China and United States of America by supporting the programme financially, and also by policies supporting entrepreneurs that would drive big and fast job growth. It also suggests that priority attention should be placed in innovation and entrepreneurship by expanding the scope of “mass entrepreneurship” innovation campaign. Wealthy and good spirited individuals should also encourage and motivate university undergraduates, irrespective of their course of study, out of school youths, people already in business to embrace entrepreneurship and innovative education as an alternative option in helping them to survive in the current and modern competitive economy and thereby escape the bitter grips of unemployment that is almost ravaging the zeal of the unemployed to be useful to the Nigerian society.

Introduction

As a service that is secured by specialized institutions, education cannot be put apart from the people who deliver the service of educating others, from their competencies and commitments. As a result, innovation and entrepreneurship in education stand as key elements in the completion of quantitative education act, which serves the socio-cultural, economic and democratic values and principles of a nation and global configurations.

Innovations and entrepreneurship, on a mass level today have become ‘very significant in view of their keys to economic development of every nation, Nigeria most especially. The objective of industrial development,

regional growth, global outreach and employment generation depend upon tactful implementation of innovations and entrepreneurship. Furthermore, managing innovations and entrepreneurship which are the seeds of industrialization development and the fruits are greater as it focuses on generation of employment opportunities to unemployed for unbiased competitive capability, increase in per capita income, higher standard of living and increased capital formation, individual savings, revenue to the government in the form of tax, sales tax, export duties, import duties, balanced regional economic growth/development and global linkages.

Eneh (2010) points out that Nigeria is yet to emerge as an exciting actor in the global scene of technological attainments. He goes further to support this claim by reference to Usoro and Enu (1997) who emphasized that a lot is yet to be done individually or collectively to really encourage Nigerians to accept modern technology as part of their culture, not alien to it, more so, as Nigerians copiously accept and appreciate products of technology but are yet to change their attitude towards entrepreneurship and innovation programs.

However, it is pertinent to throw more light on innovation and entrepreneurship education before delving into the topic.

Concept of Innovation

The concept of innovation in education management is defined as the assimilation, invention and implementation of practice structure, techniques or management process that is new to the highest level of development in the field and it is accomplished in order to contribute to reaching organizations objectives (Brikinshaw, Hamel, Mol, 2008). Being compared to other types of innovation, innovation in education management has the unique ability to operate radical and durable changes regarding the competitive edge (Harn1 & Breen: 2010). Innovations in management imply having and practicing managerial skills, determination and courage in taking responsibility for the implementation of changes that trigger progress and performance. This represents a deliberate activity, aiming to introduce novelty into a certain context. It is pedagogical because it aims to substantially improve clients/students/pupils' preparation by means of interaction and interactivity (Bécharde & Pelletier, Apud, Bécharde: 2001). Innovation in education is very important as it encourages teachers and students/clients to explore research and use all the tools to uncover something new. It involves a different way of looking at problems and solving them.

Innovation improves education because it compels students to use a higher level of thinking to solve problems. Global economy is driven by technology. Tony Wagner (2008) is quick to point out the unparalleled growth in technology that for nations survival and sustenance, it is needful for these skillset to subsist, curiosity, imagination, agility, adaptability, initiative, problem solving, critical thinking; collaboration and leadership, accessing and analysing information, effective written and oral communication.

Understandably, education in a globalized economy should go beyond preparing students for employment. It should also aspire to create students that are able to meet the needs and solve the problems of the society by taking advantage of available tools and ushering in a new and more effective way of doing things.

Innovation therefore is no longer a choice but a requirement to compete. Education therefore has the responsibility to help students to be capable of meeting this challenge by introducing such courses as:

- Use of English 1 & 11

- Principles and Practice of Management.
- Business Communication
- Micro Credit Policy and Institutions
- Management Information Systems
- Consumer Behaviour
- Business Ethics
- Small Business Finance
- Business Policy
- Investment Analysis
- Distribution and Sales Management
- Risk Management
- Human Resource Management Principles
- Principles and Practice of International Trade.
- Analysis of Finance Management, etc. (Eni, 2014).

Concept of Entrepreneurship Education

The word “entrepreneur” is derived from the French verb *entreprendre*, which means “to undertake”. This refers to those who undertake the risk of new enterprises. An enterprise is created by an entrepreneur. The process of creation is called “entrepreneurship”. An entrepreneur is a person who undertakes the development of a new venture at some risks. This implies that an entrepreneur undertakes innovations, finance and business acumen in an effort to transform innovations into economic and social goods and services. (Wikipedia, 2020). This may result in new organizations or may be part of revitalizing mature organizations in response to a perceived opportunity. Egbe (2017) interprets entrepreneurship as the act of creating new things. She describes it as a creative and innovative response to the environment and such responses can take place in any field of social endeavour, business, industry, education and social work, etc. She concludes that doing new things or doing something that is already being done in a new way is entrepreneurship. She refers to Bolarinwa (2001) to state the advantages of entrepreneurship education as follows:

1. It helps the student to form a basis of knowledge about the function and operation of a business and develop some level of familiarity and comfort with business environment since technology changes micro enterprises.
2. It plays a complementary role in developing the occupational knowledge, job skills and work experience.
3. It offers opportunities to students for job experience and for earning savings and investing money.

Entrepreneurship is the ability and readiness to develop, organize and run a business enterprise along with any of its uncertainties in order to make a profit or impact on some good on society. The most prominent example of entrepreneurship is the starting of a new business.

It is also a process of actions of an entrepreneur who is a person always in search of something new and exploits some ideas into gainful opportunities by accepting the risk and uncertainty with the enterprise. It involves a continuous search for new ideas trending on everyday experiences as basis for education

According to Drucker (2017), the purpose of every business organisation is to create and maintain a customer. Against this backdrop, he argues that managers are responsible for:

- Setting the organization's team's objectives.
- Providing and organizing the resources required to achieve the objectives.
- Motivating staff to achieve the objectives.
- Monitoring staff performance against the objectives.
- Improving performance by continually developing themselves and their staff and of course their clients.

A good number of studies have been conducted in Nigeria to investigate incorporation of entrepreneurship education into the curriculum of higher institutions. These studies discover that to assess entrepreneurship education in Nigerian institutions, it is important to understand lecturers' perceptions and determine their understanding of entrepreneurship education. Also, students' perception is needed to draw a more comprehensive picture of the entrepreneurship education situation as this could also validate teacher's views and whether the students have witnessed the kind of activities and attitudes that teachers try to complement.

Eneh (2010) contests that; Teachers, learners and policy makers involved in entrepreneurial education programs are not fully co-opted convinced nor committed to the psycho/productive aspects of these programs. Nor are they equipped to hilly conceive and develop abilities in the mindset of learners for problem solving strategies in any given context in cognitive and practical domains.

Need for Mass Entrepreneurship Education for Global Outreach in the 21st Century

Entrepreneurship education is relatively a new phenomenon in Nigerian education system in the sense that new technologies outpaced the seemingly stagnant curriculum used in schools partly due to delinquent availability of relevant supportive structures. Unlike in the United States of America, where it started and was in the curricula of tertiary institutions as far back as 947, moving on steady growth with technological research and growth (Kuralko, 2003).

Obviously, global social and economic crises have generated a heightened emphasis on entrepreneurship education it follows therefore that education is declared to be one of the main instruments for the support of entrepreneurship at all levels of the society (European Commission, 2012; 2013) in Sanusi. Olaleye & Atjonen (2017). In America, in the midst of the current crisis of effects of COVID-19 pandemic and trending Block Life Counts, an innovator/entrepreneur John Hope Bryant introduced "Operation Hope (2020). His objective is to help underserved young people have jobs and be enterprising. He opens it's the last chance to get it right in America and eradicate poverty.

Implementation Innovations and Entrepreneurship Education

To implement is to manage. Management is the act of maximizing effort, productivity and satisfaction, for conceptualized performance with minimal resources. It is the ability to sustain the implementation tempo of production in a given strategy with minimal friction whilst still upholding the vision and mission of the enterprise to the benefit of the client. Mcgrath and Bates (2017) outlines seven benefits accruing from knowledge based management approach to make one better manager a successful entrepreneur.

Analytically, they based their management theories on different platforms which includes how to; manage people, lead people, motivate staff/people/clients, act as coach, build and manage teams, analyse organizational culture, manage change, carryout strategic planning, decision making, maintain quality, exercising authority, power, influence through expertise.

It has to be emphasized that for mass innovative, entrepreneurship education democratization is imperative. It adds verve and meaning to enabling factored ways to understand, focus, commit, communicate, and determine strategies as unfailing ingredients for success in any given field.

Democratization of Innovative and Entrepreneurial Education

The federal government in realizing that innovation and entrepreneurship education is the bedrock of stimulation of the economic development of other Western countries, has made conscious efforts to democratize education. Ezeanya (2015) highlighted that education has come to be seen as the major mechanism for the upliftment and integration of the youths and citizens of a nation at large into the social, economic and political fabrics of the society. Accordingly, management of education has been a most important contributory factor to Western countries economic growth with its relative increasing investment on entrepreneurship education. Eneh (2010).

Investing in education, America improves her citizens; their economy in return is also boosted by those individuals who have been exposed to this developmental opportunity through education. This singular fact has informed all and sundry on the benefits of education thereby bringing education to involve every citizen. In Nigeria, this has caused an increase in demand for education as a road that leads to brighter opportunities in life. Adegbesan (2011) points out that education today must have the effect of making it possible for a country to have a steady supply of highly creative citizens who help to keep improving the living conditions of the general citizenry and to solve the existential problems that are thrown up from time to time.

In political parlance, democratization means freedom of all citizens of a society to participate actively in issues that concern them both directly and indirectly without limitations.

Nigeria has come a long way in getting to terms as citizens of a global identify. The consumption pattern has increasingly tended towards modern technology, products mostly imported and the country's inability to produce locally, the goods and services that the population needs. Eneh, (2010) endorsed that technology advancement is an issue to national heart, especially the indigenization of modern technology on which our economic and industrial success depends. China indigenized most of America's prototype industries and are now very close at the apex of technology, empowerment and supremacy in the global arena. Like China, Nigeria has the enabling population and are culturally imbued with natural technological ambient. A major obstruction i for Nigeria to be technologically well grounded is instituting the enabling environment (social, administration and management, finance and energy). In other words, developing the discipline to implement plans judiciously and assiduously. Eneh, (2010) intones that the present state of affairs in respect of practical training of technology education, students have not shown any improvement plan as long as industry and other employers of technology education program products are not getting really involved by way of offering necessary assistance to the training institutions. In addition, there is no democratization of opportunities for students while in training with practical exposures to such outfits through joint projects, communication, research and community bonding.

Responding to the need to produce workers with the necessary entrepreneurial skills, the Federal Government of Nigeria FGN directed all the higher education institutions in the country, to run entrepreneurial studies programme as a compulsory course for all schools irrespective of their discipline with effect from 2007/2008 academic session Okojie (2009). The above decision was taken when the FGN adopted small and medium size enterprises (SMES) as the building block of the country's economy and the right entrepreneurs to realize the objective of setting up small and medium enterprises. These were not available despite the existence of millions of unemployed youths including higher institution graduates who do not have the requisite skills and experiences of entrepreneurship in the country Nwekeagu (2015).

According to Otunla & Sanusi (2016), Nigeria recently introduced 34 trade and entrepreneurship subjects in its secondary school curriculum in 2007 to match ideas and challenges of the changing economic structure of the modern society. It is discovered that many Nigerian institutions have embraced the entrepreneurship education Nwekeagu (2013) and most of the students indicate that they had taken some courses in entrepreneurship in their respective institutions Oduwaiye (2009).

Entrepreneurship education in Nigeria amongst other things seeks to provide students in tertiary institutions with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of ventures. The concept of lifelong learning is essential to the competitiveness of the knowledge economy.

Studies have shown the impact of entrepreneurship education in individuals, institutions, economy and the society, where entrepreneurship education was recently introduced in the curriculum of some African countries including Nigeria.

Graduates from entrepreneurship programmes are three times more likely to be involved in new venture creation than non-entrepreneurship business graduates Timmons (1999), Chaney & Libecap (2000), European Commission (2015).

Strategies for Mass Innovative Entrepreneurship Education: I-Learn, U-Learn, We-Learn

Nigerian philosophy of education is not only for self-reliance but to be pacesetters in the global arena.

Akhuemonkhan, Raini and Sofoluwe (2017) revealed that Nigeria adopted entrepreneurship education in schools to accelerate economic growth and development. This, they stated is reflected in Nigeria National Policy on Education which states that education is the most important instrument for propelling change, as no fundamental change can occur in any society except through educational revolution that impact on the intellect. This therefore implies that entrepreneurship education prepares young people in business to be responsible enterprising individuals who become better and bigger global entrepreneurs who contribute to economic and social growth of their community, the nation and on global levels.

Top of the grade achievements have been recorded of Nigerians various fields of enterprise and study in various global competitive assessments. In the fields of engineering, commerce, medicine etc. they have contributed positively in their countries of residence around the globe. President Trump of the United States of America in 2019 gave a public acclaim to their great contributions to America's economic growth. According to Lovenbury (2019), the idea of infusing entrepreneurship into education resulted from reasons such as economic, job creation, individual growth and independence, increased school engagements and improved quality.

Ernoga (2008) explained that no country can move forward technologically, industrially and economically without strongly developing creative wealth through entrepreneurship education since it equips students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success.

Promoting an Entrepreneurship culture particularly entails teaching a set of cognitive and non-cognitive skills, including those that will enable students identify opportunities, take risks and also have the ability to persevere through failure.

Here are ten ways to facilitate and create innovative entrepreneurship learning for mass enterprise and productivity.

1. Mindset
2. Personality matters: create a place for all learners.
3. Use problem solving/students are loaned to the entrepreneurial outfits with problems of expertise.
4. Let students take risks and fail. (Bending with community enterprises)
5. ‘ Flipped classroom model. In ‘Go out to meet learners in context’
6. Invite entrepreneurs and innovators into the classroom.
7. Using the design-thinking process. (Projects to benefit community)
8. I-learn U-learn, we-learn online skills learning.
9. Contextualized learning centre e.g. industries, markets on their work ethics and grounds of expertise.
10. A day in a month attachment to private and public entrepreneurial outfits.

It is necessary at this juncture to introduce the I-learn U-learn strategy Asogwa & Mogboh (2020), a modified more inclusive version of the U-learn Education Centre founded in 2009 in Lirnassol Cyprus. It also tallies with NPS (2004) each one teach one campaign for mass literacy. Similarly, I-learn graduates will empower mass entrepreneurship. It empowers group learning especially in a new phenomenon of virtual learning demanding change in status quo of new age learning propensities.

The above can be embraced in both schools and out of schools scenarios through the following:

- Crossover teaching: A comprehensive understanding of learning that bridges formal and informal learning settings. Learning in schools, colleges or online can be enriched by expressions from every-day life. Informal learning can be deepened by adding questions and knowledge from the classroom.
- Teaching through smart boards
- Teaching through flipping classrooms: Flipped classroom model is an instructional strategy and a type of blended learning focused on students engagement and active learning giving the instructor a better opportunity to deal with mixed levels, students difficulties and differentiated learning preferences during in class time. It moves activities including those that may have traditionally been considered in the class. In a flipped classroom, students watch online lectures, collaborate in online discussion or carry out research at home while engaging in concepts in the classroom with the guidance of a mentor.
- Teaching through collaboration: Students learn on the job by collaborating schemes with entrepreneurs, industries and businesses.

- Teaching through virtual reality: This is a computer-generated simulation of a three dimensional image or environment that can be interacted within a seemingly real or physical way by a person using special electronic equipment. Similarly, Wikipedia (2020) points out that virtual reality is a simulated experience that can be similar to or completely different from the real world. This can be applied to education for augmented reality and mixed reality. It is useful for training and learning, meetings and everyday communication often used for augmented, collaborative and web-based for online training and learning.
- Teaching through 3D printing technology: This is described as wherein you can print objects (Patel, 2017). It makes teaching and gives a wider scope for experimentation.

However, management of entrepreneurship education thrives on expertise, seeks to provide students with the knowledge, skills and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in a variety of settings. Variations of education are offered at all levels of schooling; from primary and secondary schools through undergraduate university programs. Entrepreneurship education is also offered to out of school people, people already involved in business and organizations.

Entrepreneurship education focuses on the development of skills or attributes that enable the realization of opportunity, is focused on the best ways to operate existing learning hierarchies or businesses. Both approaches share an interest in achieving profit in some form (which non-profitable organizations or government can take the form of increased services or decreased cost or increased responsiveness to customers/citizens/clients).

The Synergy or Mass Entrepreneurship Education for Production, National Development and Global Status

Entrepreneurship education is learning directed towards developing in young and mature people these skills, competencies, understanding and attributes which equip them to be innovative, training them to identify, create, initiate and successfully manage personal, organizational and community business. And as well work for themselves Ogbuañiri (2020). He emphasized that entrepreneurship education is a pathway to job creation, poverty reduction, national and economic development that creates an opportunity curve to worldwide competitive access. He further stated that no national development or global access can take place without a robust economy that is driven by collective activities of several entrepreneurial actions. Consequently, national development as well as global access is a function of the development of individuals and corporate entities within the country and other countries. Entrepreneurship education, through its developmental impact on individuals plays a fundamental role in the development of national and global economies.

Entrepreneurship compels an individual to continuously evaluate the existing modes of business operations so that more efficient and effective system can be evolved and adopted. In other words, entrepreneurship is a continuous effort for synergy (optimization of performance) in organizations record. According to Enendu (2014), the concept of entrepreneurship is associated with a number of activities which include the ability of having a vision matched with focus and determination of building an enterprise, ability to create and build something from nothing, ability for seeing an opportunity where others fail to do so, ability to build a working team to complement the talents and efforts, ability of innovativeness and creativity, ability to take personnel and financial risks, ability to engage in activities despite all odds.

As an economic activity, entrepreneurship involves the creation and operation of an enterprise with a view to creating value or wealth by ensuring optimum utilization of scarce resources. Since this value creation activity is performed continuously in the midst of uncertain business environment, therefore entrepreneurship is regarded as a dynamic force. Moreover, emphasis is shifting from industrialized base to technology knowledge driven economy and makes more serious and enterprising the word 'competition'. Nations are in a competitive age, competing in leadership, commerce, social welfare, health etc.

Entrepreneurship is very important as it creates employment. It provides an entry-level job, required for gaining experience and training for unskilled workers. It is the incubation centre of innovation that provides new product ventures, market, technology and quality of goods etc. and increase the standard of living of the people. It also creates an impact on society and community development. A society becomes greater if the employment base is diversified. It changes society and promotes facilities like higher expenditure on education, better sanitation, fewer slums, a higher level of home ownership and improved standard of living.

Challenges of Mass Entrepreneurship Education and Proactive Measures

For these challenges to be eliminated, entrepreneurship education must be promoted in Nigeria for job and economic growth. This assertion is supported by a 2014 World Bank report which identified entrepreneurship education and training as a catalyst for innovation and job creation initiatives among university graduates especially in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) where graduate unemployment rates are high. The World Economic Forum (WEF) has also aid teaching entrepreneurship is key to combating unemployment. This suggests that entrepreneurship can be taught and learned.

However, there are some challenges of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria. Studies reveal that shortage of qualified lecturers, inadequate facilities; inadequate teaching techniques, poor funding and lack of government support hinder the effective implementation of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions Agbonlahor (2006).

Nigeria is confined with several challenges that may be resolved if it is confronted on all sides with innovative, enlightened and entrepreneurial citizens who have developed inquisitive minds to configure new ways and take exception to manage the challenges contending with them. Moreover, an emerging economy that is willing to solve the problem of joblessness will need the attention of innovative youthful minds who are willing to be educated, trained to become entrepreneurs with a start-up and anticipation to become an innovator. Thus they develop the economy, because entrepreneurs and innovators are keys to economic growth and new jobs.

Promoting an Entrepreneurship culture particularly entails teaching a set of cognitive and non-cognitive skills, including those that will enable students identifies opportunities, take risks and also have the ability to persevere through failure.

Here are ten ways to facilitate and create innovative entrepreneurship learning for mass enterprise and productivity.

1. Mindset

2. Personality matters: create a place for all learners.
3. Use problem solving/students are loaned to the entrepreneurial outfits with problems of expertise.
4. Let students take risks and fail. (Bending with community enterprises)
5. ‘ Flipped classroom model. In ‘Go out to meet learners in context’
6. Invite entrepreneurs and innovators into the classroom.
7. Using the design-thinking process. (Projects to benefit community)
8. I-learn U-learn, We-learn online skills learning.
9. Contextualized learning centre e.g. industries, markets on their work ethics and grounds of expertise.
10. A day in a month attachment to private and public entrepreneurial outfits.

It is necessary at this juncture to introduce the I-learn U-learn strategy Asogwa & Mogboh (2020), a modified more inclusive version of the U-learn Education Centre founded in 2009 in Lirnassol Cyprus. It also tallies with NPS (2004) each one teach one campaign for mass literacy. Similarly, I-learn graduates will empower mass entrepreneurship. It empowers group learning especially in a new phenomenon of virtual learning demanding change in status quo of new age learning propensities.

Since entrepreneurship education is a popular programme in the Weslein countries, Nigerians should emulate them in order to promote the programme. For instance Chen Wen Yu, an Associate Professor at Bridgewater State University in Massachusetts concludes that there is actually a strong relationship between the level of entrepreneurship education in a country and the amount of start-ups. Entrepreneurship education as well as government support for start-up at industry level is the factors that have set the United States and China apart as the world's entrepreneurial powers today. In other words, the establishment of entrepreneurship education in China and U.Ss supported by their governments, strong institutions and processes including business incubators, accelerators, and protection for patents and trademarks. Each institution or process exists to play a role to achieve entrepreneurship and innovation. Therefore, like China and U.S. A., the Nigerian government must also provide financial support for entrepreneurs and selected sectors that would drive big and fast job growth. Diversification of agriculture products and e-commerce activities will not only democratize innovation but also have created mass entrepreneurship actions.

Nigeria must develop its human capital to be globally competitive. One Way” to achieve competitiveness is by supporting strategies/entrepreneurs that will drive innovation in the economy. Training students who graduate only to become job seekers is an underutilization of the country's human resources. There is need to have a coordinated policy support to deepen entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions. For instance, schools and industries or businesses should be encouraged to take up collaborative projects in identified challenges in the society for research and implementation.

The importance of entrepreneurship education cannot be overemphasized because it prepares people to be responsible and enterprising individuals. It helps students to develop skills, knowledge and attitude necessary to achieve the goals they set out for themselves. Evidence also shows that people with entrepreneurial education are more employable. Entrepreneurship education involves all activities, aiming to foster entrepreneurial mindset, attitudes and skills and covering a range of aspects such as idea creation, start-up, growth and innovation. The

most valuable kind of entrepreneurship education would be to teach how to start a new business from beginning. This can give students ideas about the important things that need to be considered when they start new business, steps involved in it and the financial consideration.

Furthermore, high priority should be placed on innovation and entrepreneurship by expanding the scope of “mass entrepreneurship” and “innovation” campaign. The campaign involves financial support and tax incentives for entrepreneurs with the aim to make the economy innovative-driven. Innovation gives business competitive advantage. Therefore, it is important that new and would-be entrepreneurs are taught how to think creatively and innovatively. Integrating innovation and creativity into entrepreneurship education curriculum can go a long way in attracting more students, reducing graduate joblessness and boosting over-all socio-economic development. In such sphere, the strategy of ‘go out to meet learners’ in their work place would boost the number of people being trained as entrepreneurs thereby increasing their skills for competitive productivity even at global levels. Institutions of higher learning are to introduce conducting lessons in different working scenarios. For example, using opportunities in new technologies to introduce training/learning modules and skills in societal organization such as businesses, schools, churches etc. a change in curriculum status quo of schools have to change in the trending technological realities and effects of quarantine enforced by Covid-19 challenges. Both teachers and students must now embrace digital knowledge in virtual learning, modern skills block chain technologies, data processing, digital media, online research methodologies and evaluation, zoom lectures that elicit more of intellectual creative reasoning skills than traditional rendition of residual knowledge.

References

Presented at the 1st conference on the effective implementation of the federal government seven-point agenda held at NUC, Abuja.

Olutuyi, O. (2019). Promoting entrepreneurship education in Niger/a for job growth. Bellerby College.

Otunla, A.O; & Sanusi, I.T. (2016). Evaluation of teaching and learning of photography trade and its curriculum implementation in Osun State seiner secondary schools. African Journal of Education Management. 17 (2), 296-338.

Sanusi, I.T; Olaleye, S.A. & Atjonen, P. (2017). Assessment of innovative entrepreneurship education in Nigerian Tertiary institutions. Journal of Entrepreneurship Education. Vol. 20 (2).

Timmons, J.A. (1999). New venture creation: Entrepreneurship. Homewood Illinois: Irwin-McGraw-Hill.

Virtual Learning: Retrieved from www.wikipedia.org.